

Debt repayment problems: short-term and long-term implications for spending*

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Abstract

The paper investigates the economic consequences of financial difficulties. A unique quarterly panel dataset from 2004–2011 from Estonia, a euro area country, makes it possible to estimate the quarterly spending response to debt repayment problems on top of the effect of income and indebtedness. The results imply that problems lead to a substantial short-term drop in spending. Although spending recovers after the debt repayment problems are resolved, the increase is smaller than the original decline and spending remains at a lower level than before the problems emerged. An important finding is that the longer the problems last, the more severe the decline in spending is. The results suggest that the experience of debt repayment problems has severe long-term economic implications, a cost that should be taken into account when the consequences of indebtedness are assessed.

Keywords: debt repayment problems, spending, indebtedness, borrowing constraints, duration of arrears

JEL codes: D12, D14, E21, G21

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1. Introduction

The spread of debt has increased among households in recent decades, in an evolution that is also known as “democratisation of credit”. However, research on the economic implications of indebtedness started only after the 2008-2009 recession. Mian and Sufi (2009) suggest that household debt played an important role in the economic boom and subsequent bust in the 2000s by affecting households’ consumption decisions. The studies by Dynan (2012), Andersen et al. (2016) and Kukk (2016) show that the indebtedness of households does indeed affect their spending behaviour. However, these studies focus on overall household indebtedness while leaving aside the linkage between debt repayment problems and spending *on top of* the overall indebtedness. This paper contributes to the literature by exploring how debt repayment problems affect spending behaviour beyond other confounding factors, distinguishing between the effects of temporary and more persistent problems.

Debt repayment problems may affect households’ behaviour if households adjust their spending when they face financial difficulties. Furthermore, the effect can last longer than the problems as their experience of financial difficulties may lead households to make more cautious spending decisions. Several studies emphasise that indebtedness can cause anxiety and stress if unsustainable commitments lead to repayment problems (Drentea 2000, Taylor et al. 2007, Brides and Disney 2010). We explore the implications of financial difficulties further and explore whether the experience of debt repayment problems still influences spending after the problems have been solved. A study by May and Tudela (2005) suggests a contemporaneous linkage between debt repayment problems and spending but we are not aware of any study which explores the long-term effect. We see a research gap in the literature as there is a need to assess both the short-term and the long-term effects of debt repayment problems on spending.

The ability to study debt repayment problems has been constrained by the availability of suitable databases. Mocetti and Viviano (2014) point out that studies which use survey data are subject to several limitations. First, the spread of the problems in the population is relatively small, so the result is a small sample, limiting the investigation of sub-samples. And second, individuals are sensitive about revealing information on their problems and this leads to measurement error. Karlan and Zinman (2008) show that there is substantial under-reporting of consumer loans in self-reported data. There are no studies that analyse self-reporting of arrears but the issue is apparently more severe with the reporting of arrears than with the reporting of loans.

There is no issue with under-reporting when the data used are taken from loan registers which provide detailed information on loan contracts. Register data have been used to investigate the triggers of default, as in Agarwal et al. (2011) and Connor and Flavin (2015) among others. Loan register data contain quite limited information on the behaviour of the borrower beyond the given loan contract and this makes studies on the economic implications of financial difficulties rare.

The upshot of the overview is that different channels through which debt repayment problems affect spending behaviour are little explored. This paper aims to fill this gap by using quarterly individual level panel data covering around 12% of the working age population in Estonia, a euro area country since 2011. The extensive dataset from 2004 to

2011 makes it possible to trace quarterly spending and debt repayment problems over seven years. The paper takes a closer look at the quarterly spending behaviour of those who face difficulties in making their regular debt repayments. The paper contributes to the literature in several ways. First, it is possible to investigate not only short-term changes in spending but also the longer-term effect after the problems have been solved. Second, the panel dimension of the dataset makes it possible to compare the spending dynamics after debt repayment problems of different durations. Third, large dataset makes it possible to compare spending in different sub-groups. The findings provide novel insights into the relationship between spending and debt repayment problems, improving the understanding of the implications of over-indebtedness.

The results of the paper are not expected to be driven by country-specific factors and the lessons should be generally applicable. The accumulation of debt in Estonia was among the fastest in Europe in the 2000s, but the presence of debt repayment problems or arrears is comparable to that in other European countries. The EU-SILC puts the share of the population reporting arrears on a mortgage or rent at below the EU average level, as the share in Estonia was 2.7 per cent in 2010 while the EU average was 4.0 per cent.¹ Statistics from the EU-SILC suggest that the evolution of arrears in Estonia has been less pronounced than that in Spain, Italy or France and it has been quite similar to the developments in Denmark, Sweden or the Netherlands, implying that debt repayment problems have not been driven by features related to the fast rates of debt growth in the first half of the 2000s. Therefore the lessons on what debt repayment problems imply for spending behaviour are not expected to be country-specific but should be widely applicable.

The paper proceeds as follows: Section 2 discusses the literature and sets up the hypothesis while Section 3 presents the dataset. Section 4 introduces the hypothesis to be tested and the empirical model. Section 5 delivers the estimation results and provides the robustness tests. Finally, Section 6 summarises the findings.

2. Literature on the implications of financial difficulties

The standard consumption model shows that households smooth their consumption so that it depends on their lifetime wealth. Borrowing and saving allows households to follow the optimal pattern of consumption for themselves. Household debt is a negative component in household wealth, so indebtedness affects consumption negatively through the wealth effect Cooper and Dynan (2016). Edelberg (2013) argues that household indebtedness enters the consumption model beyond the standard wealth effect and the mechanism works through different channels. Financial difficulties may also affect consumption if households adjust their spending to deal with them. One mechanism through which financial difficulties can constrain spending is by hampering access to credit in the future. Credit suppliers use information about debt payment performance to assess the credit risk, which can affect the interest rate or credit limit of a borrower (Crook et al. 2007).

¹ The statistics are available from Eurostat <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database> (ilc_mdcs06).

Crossley and Low (2014) derive a model explaining how the borrowing constraint affects consumption. With the CRRA utility function where $\beta(1+r)=1$ and with binding credit constraints, the change in consumption can be written as:²

$$\left(\frac{c_t}{c_{t-1}}\right)^{-\gamma} = \frac{E_t \left[\frac{\partial V_{t+1}}{\partial W_{t+1}} \right] + \mu_t}{E_{t-1} \left[\frac{\partial V_{t+1}}{\partial W_{t+1}} \right] + \mu_{t-1}} \quad (1)$$

Where c_t denotes consumption, V_t is the value function, $E_t \left[\frac{\partial V_{t+1}}{\partial W_{t+1}} \right]$ is the expected marginal value of wealth W_t at period t , and μ_t is the multiplier on the borrowing constraint at period t . Wealth in this model specification contains both income and assets. To show the factors behind the consumption change more explicitly, eq. (1) can be rewritten as:

$$\log c_t = \log c_{t-1} - \frac{1}{\gamma} \left\{ \log \left(E_t \left[\frac{\partial V_{t+1}}{\partial W_{t+1}} \right] + \mu_t \right) - \log \left(E_{t-1} \left[\frac{\partial V_{t+1}}{\partial W_{t+1}} \right] + \mu_{t-1} \right) \right\} \quad (2)$$

Eq. (2) shows that consumption will be lower than in the previous period when the expected marginal value of wealth increases, which occurs when expected future wealth decreases. Additionally, consumption will decrease when the multiplier on the borrowing constraint increases, meaning that the constraint is more binding ($\mu_t > \mu_{t-1}$). So if households experience financial difficulties, which usually lead to tighter credit conditions, they reduce their consumption.

The use of micro-data in investigating how debt impacts consumption has increased in the last decade. Dynan (2012) uses the debt-to-asset ratio in the empirical consumption model to investigate the collateral effect on consumption. She uses the Panel Study of Income Dynamics from 2007 and 2009 and finds that highly leveraged households had weaker consumption growth than less leveraged households.

More papers investigating the effect of debt on consumption followed. Andersen et al. (2016) use yearly data from several Danish administrative registers from 2003 to 2011. They find spending during the 2008-2009 crisis to be negatively related to the initial debt-to-income ratio. Kukk (2016) investigates the effect of indebtedness using Estonian data over a business cycle and finds that a high debt service ratio constrains consumption in a recession. She explains that regular debt repayments present a financial burden to households leading to lower consumption.

The economic consequences of financial difficulties are barely explored. Duygan-Bump and Grant (2009) explore the relationship between arrears on debt and homeownership, employment, self-employment and health. They use European Community Household

² Eq. (1) combines two Euler equations, a one-period Euler equation and a two-period one.

Panel (ECHP) yearly data from 1994 to 2001 and estimate the relationship between lagged arrears and a set of variables. They find that arrears are negatively associated with future employment and homeownership and positively associated with bad health. They do not investigate the implications of arrears for spending. May and Tudela (2005) note that households in the British Household Panel Survey (BHPS) that report difficulties in making housing payments state that they have cut back on spending. To the best of our knowledge there are no other studies that explore the effect of financial difficulties on household spending behaviour.

The upshot of the literature is that some evidence suggests a negative contemporaneous relationship between financial difficulties and spending but more comprehensive studies are needed to complement our knowledge about the economic consequences of financial difficulties. The next step is to understand how much debt repayment problems impact spending on top of other confounding factors. When income, indebtedness, wealth and individual-specific characteristics are controlled for, the mechanism apparently works through financial difficulties. If problems lead to a lower credit score, spending can be hampered because households know they have limited access to credit, and will also have limited access in the future.

To examine the implications of debt repayment problems for spending, several questions should be answered. First, what is the spill-over of debt repayment problems into spending at the time of the repayment problems? The hypothesis from the literature is that households decrease their spending to cope with financial difficulties, resulting in a sharp drop in spending.

Second, how long does it take for spending to recover from debt repayment problems after the problems have disappeared? If households expect worse credit conditions even after their debt repayment problems have been resolved, the impact of financial difficulties may last longer than the difficulties themselves. The hypothesis is that the experience of debt repayment problems makes individuals more cautious about their future spending beyond the effect of income.

And third, is the spending adjustment different for temporary debt repayment problems and for long-lasting ones? As long-term problems are expected to lead to more severe credit constraints than short-term problems, the spending pattern is expected to be more conservative after severe financial problems than after temporary ones.

There may be other mechanisms at work on top of credit constraints that affect consumption through the experience of financial difficulties, such as distress. Several studies (Bridges and Disney 2010, Drenea 2000, Leung and Lau 2017, Taylor et al. 2007) find that debt repayment problems lead to increased distress, which might make households more cautious about their consumption. It is not possible from investigating debt repayment problems without observing credit conditions and distress explicitly to distinguish the role of the two factors.

3. The dataset and the properties

The paper uses anonymised quarterly panel data from a financial institution in Estonia. In Estonia the financial inclusion of the population is among the highest in Europe, as 99 per

cent of households own a bank account and both housing loans and consumer loans are taken from a financial institution (Meriküll & Rõõm 2016). On top of that, the financial sector is very concentrated in Estonia and most individuals make all their financial transactions, including borrowing, saving and life insurance, in one financial institution (IMF 2009, OECD 2011). Therefore we can claim that the data from one main financial institution provide a comprehensive picture of the financial situation of a given individual. The dataset contains financial information about individuals from the end of 2004 up to the end of 2011 and panel information about regular clients of the financial institution, covering 12% of the working age population in Estonia.³

Estonia experienced rapid economic changes in 2004-2011. Consumption grew after accession to the European Union in 2004, while unemployment was low, wage prospects good, and credit accumulation rapid. Recession hit Estonia hard in 2009 as unemployment rose and real wages fell, leading to a drop in consumption and deleveraging by households. The share of loans overdue by 60 days increased from 0.5 per cent at the end of 2007 to 4.5 per cent in 2010, since when it has gradually come down to 3.2 per cent at the end of 2011 and 0.5 per cent at the end of 2016⁴. Financial difficulties were less prevalent in Estonia than in many other European countries, suggesting that the volatile economic conditions did not lead to unsustainable borrowing. Meriküll & Rõõm (2016) show that household indebtedness is below the average level for euro area countries, suggesting strongly that the relationship between debt repayment problems and spending is driven not by country-specific circumstances but by general mechanisms which also apply to other countries.

The feature of key relevance for this study is that the dataset contains not only financial information but also quarterly outflows from the sight accounts and quarterly inflows into them. The outflows exclude payments to savings or other accounts held by an individual and payments to the financial institution, which mainly consist of debt servicing payments. The outflows from the sight accounts consist of payments, transactions and cash withdrawals, so they can be taken as a proxy for spending. It is not possible to distinguish between spending on durable and non-durable goods, which is necessary for consumption to be derived, and so total spending is the subject of investigation rather than consumption. The outflows from the sight accounts also contain real estate purchases, which should not be considered as consumption, and information about new or additional housing loans makes it possible to control these outflows in the empirical model.

Moreover, the database includes data about the quarterly inflows from legal entities (companies or other institutions) to the sight accounts of the individual. Income in Estonia is mainly paid to the sight account (Meriküll & Rõõm 2016). Therefore payments from legal entities, which contain payments of salaries, social benefits, dividends and self-employment income, can be taken as a proxy for the total disposable income of an individual.

³ The total number of private customers was 580,000 in 2004 which is 44 per cent of the total population of Estonia (http://www.seb.ee/files/aruanded/aastaraamat_2004_eng.pdf). However, a substantial share of the customers are not active customers of the financial institution; the sample for the analysis is selected from the active customers.

⁴ The statistics on loans overdue 60 days are available from the Bank of Estonia, <https://www.eestipank.ee/en/statistics>, Table 3.3.11.

The nominal variables of spending and income are deflated by the HICP consumer price index and the real variables are expressed in 2005 prices. The quarterly dynamics of the mean and median values of the two variables are provided in Figure 1. The dynamics of spending and income follow the development of the aggregate variables, showing an increase in 2004-2008 and a decline in 2009. In the model the variables are expressed in logarithms; the main statistics are given in Table A.1 in the Appendix.

The dataset contains the balance of total liabilities of each individual, including the balance of housing loans, consumer loans, overdrafts and revolving credit cards at the end of each quarter. The share of indebted individuals in the sample varies over the business cycle and follows the credit cycle. The share is at its lowest in the beginning of the sample period at 35 per cent, and peaks in 2008 at 47 per cent. The debt-to-income ratio is computed by dividing the stock of debt by the annual income from legal entities, and the debt service ratio is computed as annual debt payments divided by annual income, conditional on debt ownership. The dynamics of the mean and median values of the two ratios are given in Figure 2. There are big differences between the mean and median values of the debt-to-income ratio as the median customer does not own a housing loan, and housing loans provide the largest part of loan volumes.

This study is able to use a unique piece of information about debt repayment problems. The debt servicing payments, which contain principal payments and interest rate payments for both housing and consumer loans, are deducted automatically from the sight account by the financial institution. If an individual does not have sufficient funds on their sight account to cover their regular debt repayments, the problem is flagged until the full payment is covered.⁵ The dataset contains a flag or dummy denoting debt repayment problems at the end of each quarter. The dummy is one if there are any problems at the end of the quarter and is zero otherwise.

Figure 3 provides information on the dynamics of debt repayment problems. Both the number of individuals with problems (left-hand graph) and the share of problems (right-hand graph) were at a lower level in 2005-2007 than in 2009-2011, with a sharp increase apparent in 2008. The share of individuals with any debt repayment problems at the end of quarter rose from 0.9 per cent to 2.6 per cent among individuals with debt.

⁵ The obligation to make regular debt repayments is linked to one sight account of an individual and if the balance of this particular sight account is zero at the time of repayment, the financial institution cannot debit the payments but instead creates a flag for the problem. The other accounts of the individual are neither debited nor flagged for temporary repayment delays. More action, such as revising credit conditions, rescheduling loans, or reporting to a credit bureau, is taken once the problems persist.

Notes: The variables are expressed in EUR in 2005 prices

Figure 1. The dynamics of quarterly spending and income from 2004:Q4 to 2011:Q4 in the dataset.

Figure 2. The dynamics of the debt-to-income ratio and the debt service ratio from 2005:Q4 to 2011:Q4 in the dataset.

Figure 3. The dynamics of quarterly debt repayment problems from 2004:Q4 to 2011:Q4 in the dataset.

As there is no information about the prevalence of debt repayment problems from public statistics, the dataset has to be compared with the data from the annual EU Survey on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC), which gives some information on households' arrears. Figure A.1 in the Appendix compares the prevalence of arrears on mortgages and rents reported in the EU-SILC and the quarterly prevalence of repayment problems for any type of debt in the dataset. The prevalence of debt repayment problems in the dataset is around half of the prevalence of arrears found from the survey data, which can be explained by the different content of the two measures.⁶ The dynamics of the prevalence of financial difficulties in both datasets are quite similar, with the lowest values in 2006 and the highest values in 2010, while the prevalence of difficulties increased within that time by a factor of 2.5.

The left-hand graph in Figure 3 shows a widening gap between the number of debt repayment problems in each quarter and new problems, which are defined as debt repayment problems that appear at the end of the quarter where no problems were detected at the end of the previous quarter. The graph suggests that the duration of debt repayment problems has increased since 2008.

The panel structure of the database makes it possible to identify the duration of debt repayment problems. The number of consecutive quarters in which an individual has problems can be counted to estimate the duration of the problems. It should be noted that

⁶ The differences between the dataset and the EU-SILC emerge from several sources. First, the EU-SILC provides data for households, while individual level data are used in the dataset, and the prevalence of arrears among individuals is lower than it is among households. Second, in the EU-SILC households report arrears which occurred in the last 12 months, while the dataset records the current status of debt, suggesting that the prevalence of arrears is higher in the EU-SILC than in the dataset. Finally, it is not possible to distinguish between debt repayment problems for mortgages and those for other types of loans in the dataset, while the EU-SILC reports arrears on mortgages or rent, meaning the content of the arrears is different and is not comparable one-to-one.

when an individual faces debt repayment problems for several consecutive quarters, it is not possible to identify whether it is the same problem continuing over the quarters or whether these are different incidences. It is assumed that debt repayment problems for several quarters in a row indicate that there is a continuous problem. In the dataset individuals experienced problems for an average of 2.5 quarters. Around 76 per cent of the problems lasted only one quarter, about 13 per cent of the problems lasted for two quarters, and about five per cent of all debt repayment problems had a duration of more than three quarters.

Figure 4 shows the distribution of the duration of debt repayment problems at two different times, the end of 2006 and the end of 2009. The total duration of the debt repayment problems flagged in 2006:Q4 and in 2009:Q4 is calculated by counting all the consecutive quarters where there are debt repayment problems in both directions from 2006:Q4 and from 2009:Q4. Figure 4 confirms that the share of long-term debt repayment problems was higher during the recession in 2009 than it was during the boom in 2006.

The dataset contains information about debt servicing payments, liabilities in the form of both housing and consumer loans, and financial assets in the form of deposits, securities and pension assets at the end of each quarter, and this information can be used for control variables. The full list of the variables used in the estimations and their notation are given in Table A.1 in the Appendix.

Figure 4. The distribution of the duration of debt repayment problems for debt in 2006:Q4 and 2009:Q4.

The pooled dataset contains 2,597,000 observations across 29 quarters from 2004:Q4 to 2011:Q4, and there are 108,000 individuals in the dataset. The dataset contains individuals who were over the age of 20 in 2004:Q4 and below the age of 70 in 2011:Q4, and it contains only those individuals for whom the financial institution is identified as the main

bank for the whole period of 2004-2011, as this restriction is needed to identify the individuals for whom all or most of their financial transactions are included in the dataset.⁷

Some outliers have equally been omitted. First, all individuals who could be identified as farmers, self-employed, entrepreneurs or family doctors were excluded as it is not possible to distinguish for them between accounts used for personal and business purposes. Second, individuals with extraordinary values for financial variables are excluded. More specifically, individuals for whom any of the quarterly inflows or outflows of the sight account fall in the upper 99th or 100th percentile, individuals with a debt-to-income ratio or debt service ratio in the 99th or 100th percentile, and individuals with transactions of securities (funds, bonds and shares) in the 1st, 2nd, 99th or 100th percentile have been excluded.

4. The empirical model

We use the framework of Crossley and Low (2014) and eq. (2) to set up an empirical model in which log spending ($\log c$) is a dependent variable, and lagged log spending, log income ($\log y$), the debt-to-income ratio (DTI), the debt service ratio (DSR), a dummy for debt repayment problems (DA) and the asset-to-income ratio are the main explanatory variables. The empirical model resembles the debt augmented consumption model introduced by Ludvigson (1999) and extended by Dynan (2012), Andersen et al. (2016) and Kukk (2016). The previous studies on indebtedness have focused on biannual or yearly consumption while the current paper investigates quarterly spending over 29 quarters. A dynamic model is preferred as it includes several lags to capture a possibly delayed quarterly response of spending to a set of explanatory variables. Eight lags are included for all the explanatory variables to avoid the lags of debt repayment problems picking up any effect from the lags of the other explanatory variables. Moreover, three leads are included so that spending can be explored before the actual debt repayment problems arise. The following model is estimated:

$$\log c_{it} = u_i + \sum_{k=1}^8 \rho_k \log c_{it-k} + \sum_{k=3}^8 \beta_k \log y_{it-k} + \sum_{k=3}^8 \gamma_k DA_{it-k} + \sum_{k=0}^8 \phi_k DTI_{it-k} + \sum_{k=0}^8 \psi_k DSR_{it-k} + \sum_{k=0}^8 Z'_{it-k} \alpha_k + \tau_t + \nu_s + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

The index i denotes an individual person, t indexes time, and k stands for the number of lagged quarters. As $\log c_{it-k}$ is the log of real spending the coefficient ρ_k gives the AR(k) parameter. The variable $\log y_{it-k}$ stands for the log real disposable income of individual i in quarter $t-k$ and the coefficient β_0 depicts the response of spending to income within the quarter. The estimated parameters $\beta_1 \dots \beta_8$ depict the spending response to the lagged income, as spending may respond sluggishly to income. The estimated leading coefficients express the spending adjustment in advance of income change. Theory suggests that

⁷ The dataset contains individuals who are considered to be *regular bank clients*, which means they have income transferred to their sight account regularly. The definition of a regular bank client has been provided by the financial institution.

consumption adjusts to expected income changes and therefore the three leads of the income variable are also included, otherwise the dummy for debt repayment problems may pick up this effect. Including income in the model also addresses the correlation of a dummy for debt repayment problems with income, as the main trigger for problems is a decline in income (Agarwal et al. 2011, Connor and Flavin 2015, Kukk 2016).

The variable DA_{it-k} denotes a dummy for debt repayment problems and the coefficient γ_0 shows the relationship between the debt repayment problem and spending in the same quarter. The coefficient γ_0 gives the contemporaneous relationship between a debt repayment problem and spending while γ_1 gives the association between spending and a debt repayment problem which occurred in the previous quarter. Further lags, $\gamma_2 \dots \gamma_8$ present the effect of a debt repayment problem on spending two to eight quarters later. This model specification makes it possible to analyse the dynamics in how debt repayment problems impact spending from three quarters before and eight quarters after the problems occur.

The variable DTI_{it-k} denotes the debt-to-income ratio and the variable DSR_{it-k} stands for the debt service ratio in the period $t-k$. These variables are included to avoid the dummy for the debt repayment problem picking up other mechanisms beyond debt repayment problems as detected by Dynan (2012), Andersen et al. (2016) and Kukk (2016). As liabilities is one component of wealth, the debt-to-income ratio is expected to capture the negative wealth effect. The debt service ratio controls for the changes in the debt burden which can be related to debt restructuring. As these control variables are included in the model, the dummy for debt repayment problems estimates the effect of financial difficulties on spending on top of the effect of overall indebtedness and the debt burden.

The vector Z_{it-k} contains other control variables which may affect spending. As the spending variable expresses outflows from sight accounts, additional controls have been added to the model such as dummies for new or additional mortgages, which are used for home purchase and are recorded in the outflows from the sight accounts. Additionally, the financial asset-to-yearly income ratio is included, as spending also depends on non-human wealth (Cooper and Dynan 2016).

The individual fixed effects u_i are included to control for time-invariant unobserved individual characteristics that may affect spending while correlating with the dummy for debt repayment problems. Hence the between estimator provides spending adjustment by an individual to debt repayment problems *ceteris paribus*, where the counterfactual is spending of the same individual without repayment problems.

As explained in Section 3, there were major changes in the economic environment during the sample period, and this is expected to have affected consumer spending. To control for the effect of aggregate shocks on spending, quarterly time dummies τ_t are included. Seasonal dummies v_s are also added to capture any seasonal fluctuation in spending. Finally, ε_{it} is an error term.

5. Estimation results

5.1. Baseline estimations and robustness analysis

To give a straightforward picture of the results, the estimated coefficients and standard errors for dummies of debt repayment problems are presented graphically in Figure 5. The estimated coefficients γ_k in equation (1) are given in Table A.2 in the Appendix and the estimated coefficients for the other explanatory variables in equation (1) are given in Table A.3 in the Appendix. Before focusing on the dummies of debt repayment problems, we should comment on the other variables. First, the estimated coefficient for the lagged dependent variable is 0.07, suggesting that spending exhibits very low quarterly persistence and therefore the use of the fixed effects model is not a concern.⁸ Second, the estimated coefficient for current income is 0.37, which is consistent with the estimations by Kukk et al. (2016).⁹ We see a short-term hump-shaped relationship between spending and the debt-to-income ratio that supports the spending normalisation hypothesis explained by Andersen et al. (2016), even when housing loans determine the average DTI ratio rather than consumer loans, as given in Section 3.

The estimated model provides the quarterly response of spending to debt repayment problems and the response is estimated over 12 quarters, starting three quarters before the problems appear and running until eight quarters after. In Figure 5 the quarters are given on the x-axis, where zero indicates the quarter when an individual falls into debt repayment problems, negative numbers refer to the quarters before the problems arise and positive numbers refer to the quarters after the start of the problems.

The left-hand side graph in Figure 5 reveals that there has already been some adjustment in spending before debt repayment problems occur. Spending is on average 4.5 per cent lower in the quarter before the debt repayment problems (quarter $k = -1$). This result indicates that when financial difficulties arise, individuals react by cutting their spending to avoid or delay any debt repayment problems. The decline is quite small compared to the spending decline in the quarter when the problems appear, suggesting that the adjustment *ex ante* is modest and the main effect on spending occurs after the debt repayment problems have materialised.

⁸ Although Nickell (1981) finds that the fixed effects estimations are biased when a dynamic model is used, Monte Carlo simulations show that the bias of the estimated AR coefficient is marginal and the bias of the estimated coefficients for other explanatory variables is almost non-existent when the autoregressive coefficient is below 0.2 (Judson and Owen 1999). We considered estimating the model without the lagged dependent variable as the inclusion of the variable does not affect the results, but as we control for lags of other explanatory variables, the lagged dependent variable has been included for consistency.

⁹ They use the Estonian Household Budget Survey to investigate the consumption response to income shocks of different persistence and find that total consumption reacts to income shocks by 0.3–0.4 depending on the persistence of the income shock.

Figure 5. The estimated coefficients for dummies of debt repayment problems in spending from equation (3). The effect on spending is estimated from three quarters before the problems occur (Quarter = -3) until eight quarters after the problems have appeared (Quarter = 8).

Notes: The solid line gives the estimated coefficient for the dummies and the dashed line denotes the standard errors of the estimated coefficients. The full sample includes all the individuals in the dataset while the indebted sample contains the individuals with debt. The point estimates and standard errors are provided in Table A.2. in the Appendix.

Spending is 17 per cent lower in the quarter when an individual faces a debt repayment problem (quarter $k = 0$). This drop can be linked directly to the debt repayment problems as we control for changes in income, the debt-to-income ratio, the debt service ratio and the asset-to-income ratio. It implies that spending can also change because of other factors such as a negative income shock and an increased debt burden, but it declines by 17 per cent on top of that because of debt repayment problems.

Spending recovers to some extent in the next quarter, and the estimated coefficient of 0.129 indicates that the recovery is slight and spending is still substantially lower in the quarter following the debt repayment problems (quarter $k = 1$). Spending recovers further two quarters after the problems (quarter $k = 2$), and it is on average 5 per cent lower. There does not seem to be any additional recovery in spending in the following quarters, and eight quarters after the debt repayment problems are experienced (quarter $k = 8$), it is still 4 per cent lower than it would have been had there been no problems.

Additional estimations have been carried out for the sub-sample that contains only individuals who are indebted. The results are presented in the right-hand side graph in Figure 5 while the estimated coefficients are provided in Table A.2 in the Appendix. The spending pattern related to debt repayment problems is identical to that for the full sample, suggesting that the estimated coefficient for debt repayment problems does not capture any selection bias.

To find the sensitivity of the results to the set of variables in the model, estimations were run using only one explanatory variable with lags, the dummies for debt repayment problems, and starting to include other explanatory variables into the model one by one. The estimations are provided in Table A.4 in the Appendix. The estimated coefficients for debt repayment problems are somewhat lower when the dummies are the only explanatory variable in the model, apparently picking up the correlation with income. When the income variable is included in the model, the estimated coefficients are very stable over the different sets of explanatory variables. The exercise suggests that the results in Figure 5 do not pick up any effect other than the relationship between debt repayment problems and spending on top of the effect of income and indebtedness on spending.

5.2. Estimations by sub-groups

Before we estimate an extended model where we distinguish debt repayment problems of different durations, we analyse the stability of the results across different socio-economic groups. Several studies indicate differences in the credit behaviour of husbands and wives, as husbands perceive their financial situation to be better than wives do, while wives are more concerned about financial difficulties than husbands are (Breunig et al. 2007). Other studies do not investigate couples as such but analyse gender differences, and Keese (2012) for example finds that women feel a debt burden to be higher than men do, while Taylor et al. (2007) show that women exhibit higher mental costs from late payments. The current dataset does not contain links between household members but the comparison between male and female borrowers still provides valuable information about the gender differences in how spending responds to the experience of debt repayment problems. The differences are not induced by different economic factors as these are controlled for, so the differences between genders arise from non-economic factors.

The dynamics of debt repayment problems by gender are given in the right-hand side graph in Figure 6. The share of individuals with debt repayment problems is slightly higher among men than among women but the dynamics over the sample period are very similar.

The results of equation (1) for men and women separately are given in the left-hand side graph in Figure 7 and the point estimates with standard errors are provided in Columns (3) and (4) in Table A.2 in the Appendix. The spending response related to debt repayment problems is slightly stronger for women than for men, as spending declines by 18 per cent for women and 16 per cent for men in the quarter when they face debt repayment problems. The adjustment is quite similar for both men and women. Women exhibit somewhat lower spending when they have debt repayment problems than men do, indicating that the drop in spending might be related to non-economic factors like distress.

Figure 6. The share of individuals with debt repayment problems by gender (left graph) and age group (right graph) from 2005:Q3 to 2011:Q4, conditional on debt ownership.

Figure 7. The estimated coefficients for dummies of the debt repayment problem in equation (3) from three quarters before the problems occur until eight quarters after the problems have appeared.

Notes: The dependent variable is log total spending. The estimations are run for each sub-group separately. The point estimates and standard errors by gender are provided in Table A.2. and by age groups in Table A.5 in the Appendix.

Additional estimations are carried out for three different age groups of individuals younger than 35, individuals aged 35-50 and individuals aged over 50 at the beginning of the sample period 2004:Q4. The right-hand side graph in Figure 6 shows that there is a slightly higher share of individuals with debt repayment problems in the youngest age group than in the other two age groups. The life-cycle model suggests that young age groups need more credit, meaning they are more affected by credit constraints (Jappelli 1990). We can explore further whether the negative consequences of indebtedness in the form of debt repayment problems spill over into spending across age groups.

The estimations of equation (1) for each age group are given in the right-hand side graph in Figure 7, while the point estimates with standard errors are provided in Table A.5 in the Appendix. The decline in spending related to a debt repayment problem is 19 per cent among individuals aged below 35 and 16 per cent in the age group 35-49, while there is a 13 per cent decline among those over 50. Similarly, spending in the following quarters is somewhat lower in younger age groups than it is for the over-50s. This means the results across age groups are in line with the credit constraints across the life cycle as explained by Jappelli (1990).

Another set of estimations has been done for individuals who resided in the capital region at the beginning of the sample period, in 2004:Q4, and for individuals who lived in other regions. As indebtedness is also affected by the credit supply and there is stiffer competition among credit institutions in the capital region, the differences in the estimations between the capital and other regions may indicate that the estimations are affected by a selection due to supply-side factors. The average spread of debt was 45 per cent in the capital region and 42 per cent in other regions in the sample, while the spread of debt repayment problems among the indebted is 1.5 per cent in the capital region and 1.9 per cent in other regions. The estimations are provided in Columns (5)-(6) in Table A.4 in the Appendix and show that there are no regional differences in the spending adjustment to debt repayment problems, so selection due to regional differences does not alter the results.

All the estimations across different socio-economic groups follow the expected pattern, indicating that the estimations are robust. The results suggest that the experience of debt repayment drastically affects short-term spending, and it also changes spending behaviour in the longer term.

5.3. Estimations for debt repayment problems of different durations

It is not clear from equation (2) whether the spending decline is temporary and spending recovers after problems, as the problems may last for several consecutive quarters. Spending might respond differently to problems of a different duration as long-term debt repayment problems are more pressing than short-term problems. There is no micro-level research comparing the effect of debt repayment problems of different durations as data on the duration of the problems are very rare. This is the first paper to identify the implications of the duration of problems on spending.

The cases of debt repayment problems of different durations are categorised. The problems are divided into five groups based on their duration. The first group contains debt repayment problems which last for only one quarter, the second group contains problems which last for two consecutive quarters, and so on so that the fifth group contains debt repayment problems which last five or more consecutive quarters. Figure 4 in Section 3

gives the distribution of the duration of debt repayment problems in two time periods (2006:Q4 and 2009:Q4) and Table 3 shows the share of all problems over the sample period which last for the specified number of quarters. Debt repayment problems which last for several consecutive quarters are counted as one case rather than the quarters with problems being counted separately.

Table 1 shows that the majority of debt repayment problems, 75.5 per cent, are temporary, lasting only one quarter, while the share of problems which last five or more quarters is 4.5 per cent.

Table 1. The distribution of the duration of debt repayment problems

Number of quarters with debt repayment problems	Number of cases of problems	Share of cases of problems
1	8367	75.5%
2	1421	12.8%
3	554	5.0%
4	243	2.2%
≥ 5	498	4.5%
Total	11083	100.0%

It is important to detect when individuals fall into problems that last longer than one quarter. To do this, the dummy for debt repayment problems in equation (1) is replaced by a dummy for *falling* into problems in the given quarter. This specification helps to show how spending responds to the individual falling into problems and how spending moves after the problems have disappeared. The dummy is 1 when the quarter is the first quarter when the debt repayment problems appear, meaning that there were no problems in the previous quarter. The dummy takes the value zero if there are problems in this particular quarter but the problems started in an earlier quarter. The dummy for falling into debt repayment problems is interacted by a categorical variable which denotes the duration of the problems.

The following extended model of equation (3) is estimated:

$$\log c_{it} = u_i + \sum_{k=1}^8 \rho_k \log c_{it-k} + \sum_{k=3}^8 \beta_k \log y_{it-k} + \sum_{l=1}^5 \sum_{k=3}^8 \gamma_{lk} (N_l^{dur} \times DA_{it-k}) + \sum_{k=1}^8 \phi_k DTI_{it-k} + \sum_{k=0}^8 \psi_k DSR_{it-k} + \sum_{k=0}^8 Z_{it-k} \alpha_k + \tau_t + \nu_s + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (4)$$

In equation (4) the additional categorical variable N_l is interacted with three leads and eight lags of the dummy for falling into debt repayment problems. The index l indicates the duration of problems, from one quarter to five or more quarters. The estimated coefficient γ_{lk} gives the effect on spending of repayment problems which last l quarters.

The estimated coefficients and standard errors are provided in Table A.6 in the Appendix. Figure 8 provides the point estimates of the coefficients for the dummies of debt repayment problems which last a different number of quarters, showing the average effect on spending. As expected, the spending response is different for problems of different duration. When the problems last only one quarter (the solid line in Figure 8), spending declines in that quarter by 16 per cent on average and approximately half of the recovery occurs in the following quarter. Six quarters after the debt repayment problems appear, spending is still three per cent lower than it would have been without the experience of the problems. Spending remains at this level in subsequent quarters.

Figure 8. Estimated coefficients in equation (4) for dummies of debt repayment problems of different durations. From three quarters before the problems occur until eight quarters after the problems have appeared.

Notes: The dependent variable is log total spending. The point estimates with standard errors are provided in Table A.6. in the Appendix.

When the problems last two quarters (the long dashed line in Figure 8), spending declines by 20 per cent in the first quarter and it declines further in the following quarter, so that spending is 30 per cent lower. The major recovery in spending takes place in the next two quarters after the repayment problems have been resolved. Spending remains approximately six per cent lower even six quarters after the debt repayment problems have disappeared, suggesting that it remains subdued for a relatively long time because of the experience of debt payment problems.

When problems last longer, for three, four or five quarters, the main adjustment in spending takes place in the first quarter after the problems are first faced, and the recovery is seen in the quarter after the problems have disappeared. It is worth noting that the recovery in spending is lower the longer the debt repayment problems last.

The results by duration of debt repayment problems provide new insights into the linkages between financial difficulties and spending as there is no research distinguishing between temporary and longer-term problems. The estimations reveal that debt repayment problems affect spending quite severely. The quarterly declines in the spending of individuals with debt repayment problems are substantial at 20–40 per cent. The longer-term implication is that spending remains at a lower level after the repayment problems have disappeared, as all the estimated coefficients are negative several quarters after spending recovers from the problems. The longer-term depression of spending might be caused either by limited access to credit in the future or by distress. It is apparent that the experience of debt repayment problems makes individuals more cautious about their spending and the more severe the problems have been, the more they constrain their future spending.

6. Conclusions

This paper contributes to the literature on the implications of household indebtedness by providing novel insights into the consequences of debt repayment problems for spending. The empirical literature on the topic is rare, mainly because there is a lack of suitable data. This paper uses extensive quarterly panel data from 2004–2011 to detect the quarterly spending changes which are associated with debt repayment problems. As the effect of income and indebtedness on spending is controlled for in the model, the effect of debt repayment problems on spending indicates additional mechanisms through which credit affects spending, such as credit constraints or distress. The estimations are run using a fixed effects model controlling for other determinants of spending and controlling for time-invariant individual effects, aggregate shocks and seasonal fluctuations. The results are robust to different sets of control variables in the model.

The estimations show that debt repayment problems induce substantial spending fluctuations. The problems are associated with a decline in quarterly spending of 17 per cent on average. Younger age groups respond more strongly to debt repayment problems and this also applies tentatively to female borrowers. Additional estimations show that the magnitude of the spending decline depends on the duration of the debt repayment problems. A more substantial decline in quarterly spending of up to 40 per cent is found when the problems last for several quarters.

Spending increases only after individuals have overcome their debt repayment problems, and the main recovery occurs in the first quarter after the problems have been resolved. An important finding is that in most cases the recovery after the problems is smaller than the decline associated with the debt repayment problems and the longer the problems last, the smaller the subsequent recovery is. The finding is in line with the model with credit constraints when financial difficulties lead to tighter credit conditions. The results suggest that the experience of debt repayment problems makes individuals more cautious about their spending even after the problems have been solved. The more severe the problems have been, the more households constrain their future spending.

The novel finding about the short-term and the long-term effects of the repayment problems on spending help give an understanding of the role of household debt in spending behaviour. Recent studies have sought to assess how household indebtedness constrained spending in the 2008–2009 recession through various channels such as spending

normalisation, the wealth effect and the debt burden. These studies aim to explain the short-term fluctuations in consumption. We show that the experience of financial difficulties not only affects spending contemporaneously but also has longer-lasting consequences, indicating the importance of monitoring the financial fragility of households and implementing policies that can alleviate financial difficulties.

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Appendix.

Figure A.1. The prevalence of arrears in the total population in the EU-SILC and the dataset from 2004 to 2011

Table A.1. Definitions of all the variables used in the empirical model with summary statistics.

Variable	Definition	Mean	St. dev.
$\log y_{it}$	Logarithm of real yearly inflow from legal entities to sight accounts of individual i in quarter t , in EUR in 2005 prices	7.073	0.862
$\log c_{it}$	Logarithm of real yearly outflows from the sight account of individual i in quarter t , excluding transactions between saving and investment accounts, in EUR in 2005 prices	7.270	0.801
DA_{it}	Dummy = 1 if the individual has a flag for debt repayment problems at the end of quarter t , otherwise = 0	0.008	0.087
DTI_{it}	Debt-to-yearly income ratio, including housing and consumer loans, overdrafts and credit card balance; debt stock is measured at the end of quarter t and income is the sum of the income of the four previous quarters	0.574	1.647
DSR_{it}	Ratio of annual debt service payments for all types of loans to annual income in quarter t	0.138	0.265
FA_{it}	Ratio of financial assets to yearly income from legal entities at the end of quarter t . Financial assets include deposits, investment funds, stocks, bonds and pension funds	0.660	51.923
$\text{new}H_{it}$	Dummy = 1 if the individual owns a housing loan in quarter t while not having any housing loan in quarter $t-1$, otherwise = 0	0.002	0.047
$\text{add}H_{it}$	Dummy = 1 if the size of the individual's housing loan in quarter t exceeds the housing loan in quarter $t-1$ and the individual owns the housing loan in quarter $t-1$, otherwise = 0	0.005	0.072

Table A.2. Spending model with dependent variable $\log c_{it}$. Parameter estimates for the dummy of debt repayment problems.

	(1) Baseline	(2) Indebted	(3) Males	(4) Females
Quarter $t+3$	-0.017*** (0.005)	-0.018*** (0.005)	-0.010 (0.008)	-0.021*** (0.007)
Quarter $t+2$	-0.018*** (0.005)	-0.018*** (0.005)	-0.008 (0.008)	-0.024*** (0.007)
Quarter $t+1$	-0.045*** (0.005)	-0.048*** (0.005)	-0.040*** (0.008)	-0.047*** (0.007)
Quarter t	-0.172*** (0.006)	-0.160*** (0.006)	-0.161*** (0.009)	-0.179*** (0.007)
Quarter $t-1$	-0.129*** (0.006)	-0.129*** (0.006)	-0.122*** (0.009)	-0.133*** (0.008)
Quarter $t-2$	-0.053*** (0.005)	-0.054*** (0.005)	-0.060*** (0.008)	-0.049*** (0.007)
Quarter $t-3$	-0.040*** (0.005)	-0.040*** (0.005)	-0.033*** (0.008)	-0.046*** (0.007)
Quarter $t-4$	-0.039*** (0.005)	-0.045*** (0.005)	-0.033*** (0.008)	-0.046*** (0.007)
Quarter $t-5$	-0.037*** (0.005)	-0.041*** (0.005)	-0.027*** (0.008)	-0.044*** (0.007)
Quarter $t-6$	-0.030*** (0.005)	-0.033*** (0.006)	-0.026*** (0.008)	-0.033*** (0.008)
Quarter $t-7$	-0.036*** (0.006)	-0.034*** (0.006)	-0.037*** (0.009)	-0.035*** (0.007)
Quarter $t-8$	-0.043*** (0.006)	-0.039*** (0.006)	-0.030*** (0.008)	-0.053*** (0.008)
R^2	0.228	0.379	0.247	0.222
No. of groups	96 672	53 352	36 453	60 219
No. of obs.	1 183 831	516 319	431 455	752 376

Notes: FE estimation of eq. (3). The row in bold denotes the contemporaneous response of spending to debt repayment problems. The subsample of the indebted contains individuals whose balance of liabilities is positive. All explanatory variables and time dummies are included in the estimations but are not reported. Standard errors are reported in parentheses below the coefficient estimates, SE estimates are robust to disturbances that are heteroskedastic and autocorrelated. Superscripts ***, ** and * indicate that the coefficient is statistically different from 0 at the 1%, 5% and 10% level respectively.

Table A.3. Estimations for all the explanatory variables in the baseline model. Dependent variable: $\log c_{it}$.

Coefficients:	(1) $\log c_{it}$	(2) $\log y_{it}$	(3) DA_{it}	(4) DTI_{it}	(5) DSR_{it}	(6) FA_{it}
Quarter $t+3$		0.013*** (0.001)	-0.017*** (0.005)			
Quarter $t+2$		0.020*** (0.001)	-0.018*** (0.005)			
Quarter $t+1$		0.031*** (0.001)	-0.045*** (0.005)			
Quarter t		0.366*** (0.003)	-0.172*** (0.006)	0.047*** (0.004)	-0.025*** (0.008)	-0.082*** (0.026)
Quarter $t-1$	0.073*** (0.003)	0.094*** (0.002)	-0.129*** (0.006)	-0.042*** (0.005)	-0.168*** (0.009)	0.165*** (0.032)
Quarter $t-2$	-0.002 (0.003)	0.035*** (0.002)	-0.053*** (0.005)	-0.002 (0.004)	0.029*** (0.008)	-0.039** (0.017)
Quarter $t-3$	-0.016*** (0.002)	0.029*** (0.002)	-0.040*** (0.005)	0.001 (0.003)	0.024*** (0.007)	0.015** (0.007)
Quarter $t-4$	0.029*** (0.002)	0.005 (0.003)	-0.039*** (0.005)	-0.001 (0.003)	0.005 (0.007)	0.007*** (0.002)
Quarter $t-5$	-0.037*** (0.002)	0.024*** (0.002)	-0.037*** (0.005)	-0.006** (0.003)	-0.044*** (0.007)	-0.004 (0.004)
Quarter $t-6$	-0.044*** (0.002)	0.034*** (0.002)	-0.030*** (0.005)	0.000 (0.003)	-0.018** (0.007)	0.019*** (0.004)
Quarter $t-7$	-0.036*** (0.002)	0.025*** (0.002)	-0.036*** (0.006)	-0.004* (0.003)	-0.029*** (0.007)	0.004 (0.004)
Quarter $t-8$	-0.004*** (0.001)	0.000 (0.001)	-0.043*** (0.006)	-0.007*** (0.002)	-0.042*** (0.006)	0.001 (0.001)
R^2		0.244				
No. of groups		106 381				
No. of obs.		1 973 996				

Notes: FE estimation of eq. (3). Time dummies are included in the estimations but not all are reported. Standard errors are reported in parentheses below the coefficient estimates, SE estimates are robust to disturbances that are heteroskedastic and autocorrelated. Superscripts ***, ** and * indicate that the coefficient is statistically different from 0 at the 1%, 5% and 10% level respectively.

Table A.4. Robustness test of the estimated coefficient of debt repayment problems in the baseline model. Dependent variable: $\log c_{it}$.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Da_{it+3}	-0.030*** (0.007)	-0.027*** (0.005)	-0.025*** (0.005)	-0.023*** (0.005)	-0.018*** (0.005)	-0.018*** (0.005)
Da_{it+2}	-0.039*** (0.007)	-0.030*** (0.005)	-0.026*** (0.005)	-0.025*** (0.005)	-0.020*** (0.005)	-0.020*** (0.005)
Da_{it+1}	-0.077*** (0.007)	-0.058*** (0.005)	-0.055*** (0.005)	-0.054*** (0.005)	-0.049*** (0.005)	-0.049*** (0.005)
Da_{it}	-0.268*** (0.007)	-0.194*** (0.006)	-0.188*** (0.006)	-0.190*** (0.006)	-0.183*** (0.006)	-0.183*** (0.006)
Da_{it-1}	-0.183*** (0.007)	-0.151*** (0.006)	-0.135*** (0.006)	-0.132*** (0.006)	-0.125*** (0.006)	-0.123*** (0.006)
Da_{it-2}	-0.090*** (0.007)	-0.073*** (0.005)	-0.061*** (0.005)	-0.058*** (0.005)	-0.052*** (0.005)	-0.052*** (0.005)
Da_{it-3}	-0.063*** (0.007)	-0.053*** (0.005)	-0.049*** (0.005)	-0.047*** (0.005)	-0.042*** (0.005)	-0.041*** (0.005)
Da_{it-4}	-0.073*** (0.007)	-0.053*** (0.006)	-0.048*** (0.005)	-0.044*** (0.005)	-0.040*** (0.005)	-0.038*** (0.005)
Da_{it-5}	-0.055*** (0.007)	-0.045*** (0.005)	-0.047*** (0.005)	-0.045*** (0.005)	-0.040*** (0.005)	-0.041*** (0.005)
Da_{it-6}	-0.041*** (0.007)	-0.028*** (0.006)	-0.038*** (0.006)	-0.036*** (0.006)	-0.033*** (0.006)	-0.032*** (0.006)
Da_{it-7}	-0.044*** (0.007)	-0.030*** (0.006)	-0.044*** (0.006)	-0.041*** (0.006)	-0.037*** (0.006)	-0.037*** (0.006)
Da_{it-8}	-0.058*** (0.007)	-0.041*** (0.006)	-0.050*** (0.006)	-0.048*** (0.006)	-0.045*** (0.006)	-0.043*** (0.006)
$\log c_{it-k}$	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES
$\log y_{it-k}$	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
DTI_{it-k}	NO	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
DSR_{it-k}	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES	YES
FA_{it-k}	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	YES
newH_{it-k}	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
R^2	0.021	0.176	0.187	0.191	0.193	0.210
No. of groups	96 672	96 672	96 672	96 672	96 672	96 672
No. of obs.	1 183 831	1 183 831	1 183 831	1 183 831	1 183 831	1 183 831

Notes: FE estimation of eq. (3). All explanatory variables and time dummies are included in the estimations but not all are reported. Standard errors are reported in parentheses below the coefficient estimates, SE estimates are robust to disturbances that are heteroskedastic and autocorrelated. Superscripts ***, ** and * indicate that the coefficient is statistically different from 0 at the 1%, 5% and 10% level respectively.

Table A.5. The estimated coefficient of debt repayment problems in the baseline model for different sub-samples. Dependent variable: $\log c_{it}$.

	(1) Age < 35	(2) Age 35 – 50	(3) Age > 50	(5) The capital region	(6) Other regions
Da_{it+3}	-0.014* (0.008)	-0.017** (0.008)	-0.016 (0.011)	0.003 (0.009)	-0.023*** (0.006)
Da_{it+2}	-0.017** (0.008)	-0.014* (0.008)	-0.033*** (0.011)	-0.006 (0.009)	-0.021*** (0.006)
Da_{it+1}	-0.035*** (0.008)	-0.059*** (0.008)	-0.033*** (0.012)	-0.023** (0.009)	-0.052*** (0.006)
Da_{it}	-0.191*** (0.009)	-0.163*** (0.009)	-0.127*** (0.012)	-0.163*** (0.010)	-0.174*** (0.007)
Da_{it-1}	-0.129*** (0.009)	-0.135*** (0.010)	-0.083*** (0.013)	-0.102*** (0.011)	-0.139*** (0.007)
Da_{it-2}	-0.045*** (0.008)	-0.066*** (0.008)	-0.027** (0.012)	-0.043*** (0.010)	-0.056*** (0.006)
Da_{it-3}	-0.034*** (0.008)	-0.038*** (0.008)	-0.044*** (0.012)	-0.043*** (0.010)	-0.037*** (0.006)
Da_{it-4}	-0.033*** (0.008)	-0.048*** (0.009)	-0.028** (0.013)	-0.016* (0.009)	-0.048*** (0.006)
Da_{it-5}	-0.050*** (0.008)	-0.026*** (0.008)	-0.014 (0.013)	-0.028*** (0.009)	-0.038*** (0.006)
Da_{it-6}	-0.032*** (0.008)	-0.038*** (0.009)	-0.002 (0.014)	-0.017* (0.010)	-0.034*** (0.006)
Da_{it-7}	-0.042*** (0.008)	-0.036*** (0.009)	-0.004 (0.012)	-0.026** (0.011)	-0.039*** (0.007)
Da_{it-8}	-0.040*** (0.009)	-0.046*** (0.009)	-0.040*** (0.013)	-0.038*** (0.010)	-0.043*** (0.007)
R^2	0.285	0.255	0.214	0.206	0.240
No. of groups	31 022	34 901	30 749	32 156	64 516
No. of obs.	342 854	431 395	409 582	379 415	804 416

Notes: FE estimation of eq. (3). Deposit refers to the total balance of all the sight accounts of an individual. All explanatory variables and time dummies are included in the estimations but not all are reported. Standard errors are reported in parentheses below the coefficient estimates, SE estimates are robust to disturbances that are heteroskedastic and autocorrelated. Superscripts ***, ** and * indicate that the coefficient is statistically different from 0 at the 1%, 5% and 10% level respectively.

Table A.6. Parameter estimates for the dummy of falling into debt repayment problems. Dependent variable: $\log c_{it}$.

	(1) Problems for one quarter	(2) Problems for two quarters	(3) Problems for three quarters	(4) Problems for four quarters	(5) Problems for five quarters
Da_{it+3}	-0.019*** (0.007)	-0.021 (0.016)	0.000 (0.026)	0.036 (0.038)	0.039 (0.032)
Da_{it+2}	-0.021*** (0.007)	-0.025 (0.016)	-0.015 (0.029)	0.053 (0.040)	0.007 (0.032)
Da_{it+1}	-0.047*** (0.007)	-0.062*** (0.016)	-0.026 (0.027)	-0.055 (0.036)	0.012 (0.030)
Da_{it}	-0.160*** (0.007)	-0.195*** (0.016)	-0.211*** (0.027)	-0.205*** (0.046)	-0.199*** (0.030)
Da_{it-1}	-0.121*** (0.008)	-0.314*** (0.019)	-0.351*** (0.030)	-0.297*** (0.041)	-0.372*** (0.034)
Da_{it-2}	-0.058*** (0.007)	-0.162*** (0.019)	-0.383*** (0.033)	-0.431*** (0.044)	-0.396*** (0.032)
Da_{it-3}	-0.048*** (0.007)	-0.079*** (0.016)	-0.237*** (0.038)	-0.383*** (0.038)	-0.403*** (0.033)
Da_{it-4}	-0.050*** (0.008)	-0.087*** (0.016)	-0.123*** (0.034)	-0.175*** (0.043)	-0.432*** (0.037)
Da_{it-5}	-0.041*** (0.007)	-0.067*** (0.017)	-0.130*** (0.031)	-0.150*** (0.043)	-0.344*** (0.035)
Da_{it-6}	-0.029*** (0.007)	-0.100*** (0.017)	-0.086** (0.035)	-0.077* (0.041)	-0.344*** (0.033)
Da_{it-7}	-0.034*** (0.008)	-0.042** (0.016)	-0.068** (0.030)	-0.092** (0.039)	-0.255*** (0.035)
Da_{it-8}	-0.033*** (0.007)	-0.058*** (0.016)	-0.090*** (0.028)	-0.088** (0.039)	-0.277*** (0.042)
R^2	0.228				
No. of groups	96 672				
No. of obs.	1 183 831				

Notes: FE estimation of eq. (4). Dummies for debt repayment problems. The bold denotes the quarters when the problems still last. Standard errors are reported in parentheses below the coefficient estimates, SE estimates are robust to disturbances that are heteroskedastic and autocorrelated. Superscripts ***, ** and * indicate that the coefficient is statistically different from 0 at the 1%, 5% and 10% level respectively. The coefficients in bold indicate the period with debt repayment problems.